

Effect of Capacity Building on Productivity Alcoholic Beverage Companies

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ABSTRACT

The fast moving pace of business in Nigeria seems to have caught-up with the alcoholic beverage sector of the country presumed before now to be controlled by two players. However, with the supply side of value-adding employees drying-up as our universities are being accused of churning-out poorly developed graduates, the demand side may have prompted stiff jostling or even poaching for the few managerial talents available. As a result, looking inwards through capacity building may present a viable way out of the doldrums for all concerned. To address the foregoing challenges, the study therefore examined the effect of capacity building on productivity using the two leading players in the alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector (Nigeria Breweries Plc., Lagos and Guinness Nigeria Plc) as case study. In line with extant literature capacity building which constituted the independent variable in the study was operationalized in terms of on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship as its components. Survey design, systematic and stratified sampling techniques were employed to draw a sample of three hundred and sixty (360) respondents comprising 212 (58.9%) males and 148 (41.1%) females who participated in the study. Data was collected using validated scales designed for the purpose of this study. Five (5) hypotheses were formulated and tested using simple and multiple regression analysis namely that there is no significant effects of on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship on productivity and that there is no significant effect of capacity building on productivity. The results showed that the four dimensions of the independent variable (i.e. on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship) effected significantly on productivity in the study population. Furthermore, the multiple regression analysis conducted confirmed these results as capacity building was also found to have effected significantly on productivity. These findings support the notion that enabling employees with the right blend of skills, knowledge, expertise and experience would be in the firm's best productive interests. The study therefore recommended that as the proverbial geese that lay the golden egg, employees should be exposed to on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge and organisational mentorship.

KEYWORDS: *On-the-job-training, Off-the-job-training, technological knowledge acquisition, organizational mentorship, capacity building, productivity*

INTRODUCTION

The role of human capital in the progress of the organisation cannot be overemphasized. In fact, Harvey (2013) posited that quality human capital is not just a critical driver and sustainer of organisational productivity but also a defining factor of business competitions for years to come. In view of the foregoing therefore, it would seem not out of place to add that it may be difficult for the organisation to rise above the quality of its human resource. In the considered position of Ojokuku and Adebite (2014) for example, though organizations producing competitive goods and services

could be distinguishable in terms of market share and size, it is actually the quality of human resource which pilots the affairs of each organisation that makes such market dominance possible.

However, for human resource to maintain its pride of place as the driver of organisational productivity, continuous acquisition and improvement of relevant knowledge and skills through capacity building are vital (Ojokuku & Adebite, 2014). Small wonder therefore that Anyanwu

(2002) had reported that capacity building is akin to the industrial production process of molding, tempering, shaping and sharpening which culminates in converting raw metals into finished articles. In this sense, capacity building ensures that employees' ability to contribute positively to organisational performance standards receive the desired improvements (Yamoah, 2014).

In other words, capacity building ensures that employees remain productive and economic agents in the organisation as capacity building is about imparting relevant knowledge and skills for productive purposes (Anyanwu, 2002). Further to the foregoing, it could be argued that in the absence of education, training and development organisational manpower may be viewed as passive and inactive burden or mere potentials in the productive efforts of the firm. Capacity building can therefore come in to translate the manpower into "finished articles" or productive resource by imparting the desired skills and knowledge (Anyanwu, 2002).

For Letts, Ryan and Grossman (1998), what capacity building contributes to the firm could come in form of dominance, expansion and adaptive capacities. In other words, having the right blend of human resource that is equipped with requisite skills and knowledge ensures that the firm achieves continuous improvement in its products and services thereby sustaining its dominance capacity of the market. In the same vein, having the right blend of human resource that is equipped with requisite skills and knowledge ensures that the firm grows in tandem with or even ahead of market demands thereby sustaining its expansion capacity. Similarly, having the right blend of human resource that is equipped with requisite skills and knowledge ensures that the firm could be flexible enough to respond to the ever changing demands of its market (Ojukuku & Adegbite, 2014).

In relation to the Nigerian alcoholic beverage market, the dominance, expansion and adaptive capacities of Nigerian Breweries (NB) Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc as the two major players (Euromonitor, 2016) in the sector seem to be under threat as new entrants such as SABMiller have added to the level of competition among players in terms of alteration of market dynamics and jostling for market share through successful introduction of products like *HERO* and *Castle* brands into the market (Disu, 2017).

The alcoholic beverage market is a duopoly of two global manufacturers namely Heineken and Diageo who have Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc as their respective subsidiaries (Rasaq, 2010; Euromonitor, 2016; Disu, 2017). However, with the entry of new comers such as SABMiller, the Nigerian alcoholic beverage market could no longer be taken as a two-horse race involving Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc. In order to maintain strategic positions in the market, companies had to re-strategize, re-align, re-focus and re-charge. In fact, the foregoing development may have led to mergers and acquisitions witnessed in the industry such as SABMiller with Pabod Breweries (Port Harcourt, Rivers State) Standard Breweries (Ibadan, Oyo State) and the Greenfield refinery (Onitsha, Anambra State) while Nigerian Breweries Plc did same with Sona Breweries (Ota, Ogun State and Kaduna), Life Breweries (Onitsha, Anambra State) and Consolidated Breweries Plc (Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State, Awo-Omama, Imo State and Makurdi, Benue State).

For Guinness Nigeria Plc, the competitive state of alcoholic beverage market in Nigeria may have informed the acquisition of distribution rights of McDowell's, commissioning of a local spirits production line at Benin refinery and the acquisition of the distribution rights to international premium brands like Johnnie Walker, Baileys and Cîroc. On the other hand, musical concerts, massive media advertisement campaigns, sales promos and sponsorship schemes are some of the measures being employed in the Nigeria alcoholic beverage market to stimulate buying consciousness and attract deep engagement among consumers (Disu, 2017). However, while the business terrain appear to be moving at a very fast pace in Nigeria, the supply of value-adding employees seem to be drying-up with companies in stiff jostling (or sometimes engaging in poaching) for the few managerial talents that are available. Unfortunately, the onus is on the educational sector in Nigeria, to produce skilful manpower that will fit into the labour market and raise the economy of the nation. In fact, the world over, the cardinal objective of the universities is to generate, store and transmit both specialized knowledge and sophisticated expertise relevant to businesses. Sadly, reservations are being expressed to the effect that Nigeria is saturated with graduates who are largely lacking in basic employability skills needed in the modern workplace. Today's graduates in Nigeria are not just poorly prepared for work but "half baked" to the point of obvious lack in communication skills or technical competencies. The need for capacity building therefore cannot be more evident as beer manufacturers in Nigeria need more of employees who can make decisions quickly in situations of high competition and uncertainty as well possesses the capabilities to steer organizations through wrenching change.

This study is therefore an attempt to examine the impact of capacity building on productivity using the two major players in the alcoholic beverage sector in Nigeria (Nigerian Breweries (NB) Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc) as unit of analysis. In the study, on-the-job-training, off-the-job-training, technological knowledge acquisition and mentorship are operationalized as components of capacity building.

CAPACITY BUILDING

Capacity building in business environment could be defined as measures of enhancing the quality, speed, efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery. Hence, Stringer (2013) explained that capacity building is a connotation which encompasses various efforts at equipping, reforming and improving the workforce to be prepared to face the ever rapidly changing and unpredictable business world. Furthermore, capacity building is about maintaining a culture of improvement in employees to help organisations survive a business landscape fraught with complete uncertainty (Springer, 2013). As construed by Yamoah (2014), capacity building encompasses education, training and development of human resource for the purpose of updating employee ability in tasks that meet or even surpass the performance yardsticks of the organisation. In the same vein, capacity building was defined in Pricewaterhouse Coopers (2011) as various measures geared towards equipping the enterprise for improvement in the areas of impact, achievement, relevance, core competencies, strength and dominance. For Ojukuku and Adegbite (2014), capacity building refers to various measures and programmes

designed to assist employees in either acquiring new skills or improving on the already acquired skills for the overall benefit of the enterprise.

In a study which identified training as one of the measures of building capacities in employees, Khan, Khan and Khan (2011) defined on-the-job training as practical knowledge gained when employees acquire real time experiences in performing organisational roles as compared to off-the-job training which are usually non-practical, classroom oriented and bookish in nature. Similarly, Obi-Anike and Ekwe (2014) argued that off-the-job training involves molding employees through such means as education, workshops, seminars, conferences, retreats etc. in order to achieve improved competence and efficiency required for organisational goals while on-the-job training is about exposing employees to various job roles in the organisation in order to develop expertise and confidence. As posited by Kim and Ployhart (2014), on-the-job training is construed as internally exposing employees to firm-specific opportunities or situations in order to proximally accumulate tacit skills while the firm achieves competitiveness by transferring valuable knowledge in a cost effective manner beyond the reach of its rivals. This is given that the firm's competitive capability is a reflection of the quality of its human capital (Falola, Osibanjo & Ojo, 2014). For Falola, Osibanjo and Ojo (2014), although training entails equipping employees with relevant skills, learning, competencies, abilities and knowledge needed for optimal utilization by the firm; training exercises may be conducted in-role (on-the-job training) or out-role (off-the-job training).

Information and communication technology (ICT) has emerged as veritable tool to building employee capacities as ICT could be deployed to making job-tasks easier, achieve better communication and coordination and improving overall efficiency especially in the area of real-time service delivery (Imran, Maqbool & Shafique, 2014). Oghojafor, Aduloju and Olowokudejo (2011) explained that technological knowledge acquisition is about developing skills in the use of digital appliances, telecommunications and computers for data processing and distribution in the organisation. In the same vein, Berisha-Shaqiri (2015), explained that technological knowledge acquisition is specialized form of learning geared towards improving the skills and competencies of beneficiaries in the area of information and communications technology, automation, computers, electronic gadgets, smart appliances and modern factory equipment. On their part, Imran, Maqbool and Shafique (2014) described technological knowledge acquisition as skill improvement by being familiar with use and operations of computer, internet, intranet and other technological enablers deployed in the organisation.

In addition to building employee capacities through technological skills, literature has shown that employee skills and competencies could be fine-tuned and nurtured in the course of a dyadic relationship between experienced hands in the organisation and their less experienced counterparts (Mundia & Iravo, 2014; Tewari & Sharma, 2014; Mba & Godday, 2015). For Igbaekemen (2014), organisational mentoring involves developing and nurturing the skill, knowledge and competencies of subordinates by superiors in the form of assistance, counsel, guidance, advice and experiential exposure. Similarly, Mundia and Iravo (2014) see organisational mentoring as a strategic way of

developing workforce capabilities whereby less experienced employees are encouraged to continuously learn from their superiors through exposure and guidance. As posited by Okurame (2008), organisational mentoring is about improving employee competence and capability through professional grooming which could come in the form of career development (e.g. exposure to demanding job tasks) and psychosocial intervention (e.g. role modeling, counseling, acceptance, recommendation etc.).

PRODUCTIVITY

The term productivity is without a generally acceptable and applicable meaning within the manufacturing sector (Tangen, 2002; Pekuri, Haapasalo & Herrala, 2011). However, regardless of this shortcoming, it is important that the basic features of productivity is understood in both literature and in the industry (Tangen, 2002). To this end, Tangen (2002) construed productivity in terms of input-output ratio. In other words productivity is the outcome of consumed resources (input) in relation to produced goods (output). In a related development, Wanyama and Mutsotso (2010) believed that productivity is about being mentally and physically present in a job. In other words, productivity implies the number of times an employee is available to exert physical energy in contributing or otherwise to organisational goals. In the same vein, productivity also implies the extent to which an employee could mentally contribute to organisational goals in terms of creativity, innovations, valuable suggestions and overall problem solving capability and competence. For Kim and Ployhart (2014), productivity is simply defined as the efficiency of the organisation's manpower to achieve output. Similarly, Pekuri, Haapasalo and Herrala (2011) argued that productivity is about value creation taking into consideration the use and availability of resources. In this regard, improper use or dearth of resources could result in creating less value thereby implying low productivity (Tangen, 2002; Pekuri, Haapasalo & Herrala, 2011).

CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE STUDY

Based on the foregoing conceptual explanations, a research model is developed for the study which is given below:

Source: Author (2017)

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the Study

Figure 1 shows the conceptual model that guides the study. The model also depicts an interface of the various variables in the study. In the model, it could be seen that the firms' modes of building capacities are as result of their operating environment which comes as internal (e.g. organisational culture) and external (e.g. Labour Law) factors. Furthermore, the resultant measures of building capacities from the organisations' operating environment when applied as a combination could result in a productive workforce.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study adopted the Human Capital and Resource-Based View as theories in explaining the role of capacity building on productivity. The basic assumption behind the Resource-Based View (Wernerfelt, 1984; Barney, 1991) is that firm's human resource (i.e. workforce) is source of its competitive advantage. As reported in Barney (1991), knowledge as a "resource" can enable the firm to improve its effectiveness and also serve as "strength" which the organization can leverage upon in conceiving and executing her business strategies. In essence, what the firm needs to do in commanding a sustained competitive advantage (or maintain a large market share) is to build capacities that are rare, valuable, non-substitutable, and imperfectly imitable in its employees. This study has shown on strength of previous literature that such capacities could be built through measures like on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentoring.

In similar vein, the human capital theory assumes that employees possess a set of competences and skills developed by education and training which could be deployed in the organisation to generate a stock of productive capital. In other words, it is the key competences, skills, knowledge and abilities of the workforce that contributes to organizations competitive advantage hence there is need for the organisation to support investment in human capital through human resource development activities like on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentoring. The idea of investing in human capital was first developed by Adam Smith (1776), who argued in the *Wealth of Nations* that regardless of the costs expended in building capacities by the organisation in its employees through education and training, the returns on such investments would be more than enough to accommodate the costs of acquiring those competencies.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

In a study designed to establish the relationship between capacity building and productivity, Igbaekemen (2014) found that developing employee capacities is related to productivity in the organisation especially in the area of efficiency and organisational survival. Similarly, Ojukuku and Adegbite (2014) identified capacity building as sure route to improving the productive efforts of the organisation as capacity building bestows on the employees, fresh knowledge, new way of thinking, efficiency, effectiveness and relevant skills needed for achieving competitive advantage by the organisation. For Wanyama and Mutsotso (2010), capacity building programmes stimulate mental presence and efficient disposition in employees which assist the productive endeavours. In a related study, Yamoah and Maiyo (2014) established that improved productivity in the organisation could be achieved by building employee capacities through value-intensive training programmes.

In study designed to test the impact of training as capacity building mechanism on productivity, Singh and Mohanty (2012) reported a direct relationship between the nature of training conferred on employee and productivity in a wide range of industries spanning banking, agricultural, service and consumer goods. In a similar study, Nda and Frad (2013) linked consistent learning and upgrading of skills and competence which come from training to productivity in the

organisation. For Sabir, Akhtar, Bukhari, Nasir and Ahmed (2014), value-based training undertakings in the organisation are positively related to employee productivity. Furthermore, the study identified feedback and job involvement as key issues in identifying training needs for building employee capacities required for productive endeavours in the organisation. In a related development, the results in Ombayo, Egessa and Shiamwama (2014) revealed a strong positive association between various training measures and productivity such that productivity level in the organisation rises in tune with additional training exposures. The study further linked training to stemming of leakages in the system and productive deployment of firm's resources.

In attempt to examine the impact of job training on efficiency and productivity in the organisation, the study by Eneh, Inyang, and Ekpe (2014) found significant and positive association among on-the-job and off-the-job job training, efficiency and productivity in the organisation with job training implicated in employee ability to deliver and satisfaction with the job. In the same vein, Obi-Anike and Ekwe (2014) posited that off-the-job training programmes like refresher courses and on-the-job training programmes like job enrichment assist the productive efforts of the organisation in terms of efficiency, team delivery, team bonding and commitment both in the short and long basis. A similar study conducted by Kim and Polyhart (2014) discovered that firms can build their productive capacities by selectively recruiting and selecting talents and then internally training their workforce leading to a human capital that is capable of effectively deploying resources, navigating the firm out of recession and placing the firm far above competition. Similarly, Falola, Osibanjo and Ojo (2014) found that on-the-job and off-the-job training enrich the productive efforts of the organisation in terms of skill-set and competence for optimization, creative and innovative disposition for competition as well as employee up-grading and efficacy.

Following the advent of globalisation, capacity building via technological knowledge has emerged as formidable way of making the organisation competitive (Ngure & Njuri, 2013). For instance, the study by Dauda and Akingbade (2011) posited that technological knowledge acquisition improves employee skill which in turn impacts on the quality of the production. In the same vein, Oluwagbemi, Abah and Achimugu (2011) reported that technological knowledge acquisition has brought about improved productivity in terms of quality and content such that organisations have become more competitive on account of innovative driven capacities provided various e-channels. For Berisha-Shaqiri (2015) technological knowledge acquisition has revolutionised the conduct of businesses such that employees are productively deployed by organizations to obtain strategic advantage. On the contrary, Oluwadare, Obembe and Olayungbo (2016) found that technological acquisition was negatively and insignificantly correlated with productivity in Nigerian firms; a development which the study attributed to the low absorptive capacities (i.e. low level of technological knowledge amongst employees) in Nigerian firms.

Perhaps on account of findings such as Oluwadare, Obembe and Olayungbo (2016) that led scholars like Neupane (2015) to advocate for manpower development through

organisational coaching and mentoring whereby specialized skills could be transferred from one member of the organisation to another. As reported by Kahle-Piasecki (2011), exposing employees to mentoring arrangements in the organisation enhances their skill development as appropriate knowledge needed for productivity are transferred from more experienced employees to their less experienced counterparts. Similarly, Tewari and Sharma (2014) reported that the nurturing, guidance and integration provided in the course of mentoring are useful in the productive efforts of the organisation. In the views of Mba and Godday (2015), mentoring are organisational learning relationships aimed at enhancing and developing employee job skills and potentials for improved productivity. The study further linked organisational mentoring to improved efficiency, employee performance and reduction in turnover of talented employees. In a related study, Tanoli (2016) found that employee skills and efficiency are developed in the process of mentoring relationships even to the point of tackling immediate and future challenging tasks thereby increasing the productivity and competitiveness of the firm.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The study adopted a survey design.

Area of Study: The study was carried out in Lagos Nigeria. Lagos region plays hosts to about 70 percent of all industrial investments in Nigeria with heavy concentration of multinational corporations and major financial institutions in the country (Fagbohunka, 2014) and is reputed to be Nigeria’s commercial nerve centre and its largest city (Oni, 2008). In addition to the heavy concentration of industrial activities and high population of people who are employed as part these commercial and industrial activities, Lagos was chosen because the population of interest is suited for the issues under focus.

Nature and Sources of Data: The data used in the study were obtained from primary and secondary sources. The primary data were generated from the Head offices of Nigerian Breweries Plc, Iganmu, Lagos and Guinness Nigeria Plc, Oba Akran, Lagos through a structure questionnaire specially designed for the study while the secondary sources of data in the study included relevant literature retrieved from scholarly journals, official reports, handbooks, pamphlets, internet, Newspapers, books, magazines, government gazettes, amongst others.

Population of the Study: There are sixty one (61) companies in the registers of the Association of Food, Beverages and Tobacco Employers Association in Nigeria. Part of this population is the nineteen multinational (19) corporations in the Food and Beverage industry in Lagos State, Nigeria. However, based on their specialization, level of dominance, market experience, performance and the large number of employees in the pay roll, two companies – Nigeria Breweries Plc, Iganmu, Lagos and Guinness Nigeria Plc, Oba Akran, Lagos were chosen for the study.

Incorporated in 1946, Nigerian Breweries Plc is reputed to be the first and biggest alcohol brewing firm in Nigeria. The company’s rich portfolio of alcoholic brands includes Star, Gulder, Legend Extra Stout, Goldberg, Star-lite, Star Radler, Star Triple-X etc. Nigerian Breweries Plc has ten operational breweries from which its products and services are extended

to all parts of Nigeria and other parts of West Africa (Nigerian Breweries, 2017).

Guinness Nigeria Plc was incorporated in 1962 as first subsidiary of Dageo Plc outside of the Great Britain and the United Kingdom. Guinness Nigeria Plc is reputed to be one of the two leading alcohol brewing firms in the country. The company’s rich portfolio of alcoholic brands include Harp, Guinness Stout, Guinness Extra Smooth, Satzenbrau, Smirnoff Ice, Snapp, Dubic, Orijin, Red and Black label whisky, Bailey’s Irish cream etc. Guinness Nigeria Plc has ten operational breweries from which its products and services are extended to all parts of Nigeria and other parts of West Africa (Guinness Nigeria, 2016).

Available records indicate that there are 3646 employees under the payroll of the company (Nigerian Breweries, 2017) while Guinness Nigeria Plc has a staff population of 1070 individuals (Guinness Nigeria, 2016). The foregoing statistics include members of staff who pilot the daily affairs of the companies towards achievement of the targets, goals and objectives, the supervisors who monitor the operational activities of the companies and the field workers who provide requisite skills, knowledge and attitude in order to ensure the accomplishment of organizational goals.

Determination of Sample Size: Data obtained from the appropriate authorities in the two companies under focus showed that there are 3646 employees at Nigerian Breweries Plc, Lagos. In addition, available records revealed that there 1070 employees at Guinness Nigeria Plc. Table 1 specifically shows the population and spread of employees in each of the two companies under focus (i.e. Nigeria Breweries Plc, Lagos and Guinness Nigeria Plc, Lagos).

Table 1: The Spread of Employees in the Study Population

S/N	Companies	Number of Employees
1	Nigerian Breweries Plc	3646
2	Guinness Nigeria Plc	1070
	TOTAL	4716

Source: Fieldwork (2017)

Sample Size and Sampling Technique : In order to achieve the aim of determining an appropriate sample size, the study adopted the standard formula for sample size determination as provided in Yamane (1967). The outcome is presented below:

$$\text{Given as } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

- Where n = Sample size
- N = Population
- e = Margin of Sampling Errors

Thus, using a sampling error of 0.05 and the population size being 4716 employees, the sample became:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{4716}{1+4716(0.05)^2}$$

$$= \frac{4716}{12.79}$$

$$N = 369$$

Having determined the sample size, the next task was to ensure that the sample was representative enough. To this end, the study adopted Bowley (1926) proportional allocation formula to distribute the sample into different strata for the basis of data collection. The Bowley (1926) proportional allocation formula is noted for the accommodation of the different strata of the population in a sample. The Bowley (1926) proportional allocation formula is given as:

$$n_h = \frac{nN_h}{N}$$

Where n_h = number of units allocated to each stratum.
 N = total sample size
 N_h = number of items in each stratum in the population
 N = total population

Proportion for Nigerian Breweries Plc

$$n_h = \frac{3646 \times 369}{4716} = 285$$

Proportion for Guinness Nigeria Plc

$$n_h = \frac{1070 \times 369}{4716} = 84$$

Table 2 shows the result of the results of the sample size determination and the proportional distribution of the sample into various units for the purpose of data collection.

Table 2: Sample Size and the Distribution of the Sample into Various Units

S/No	Organisation	Population	Sample
	Nigerian Breweries Plc	3646	285
	Guinness Nigeria Plc	1070	84
	TOTAL	4716	369

Source: Fieldwork (2017)

Method of Data Collection: The study employed multistage data collection procedure made up of systematic, proportionate, stratified and convenience sampling techniques. First, having employed systematic sampling technique in choosing the two companies (i.e. Nigeria Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc) out of the 19 corporations in the Food and Beverage industry in Lagos State, Nigeria, proportionate and stratified sampling techniques of Yamane (1967) and Bowley (1926) were employed in determining an appropriate sample size for the study and then proportionally distributing the sample into different strata. As argued in Welman, Kruger and Mitchell (2005), the foregoing sampling allows the researcher to deliberately obtain units of analysis in such a way that the sample may be regarded as representative of the relevant population from which it is drawn.

In collecting the data proper, the researcher approached the management of Nigerian Breweries and Guinness Nigeria Plc for relevant authorisation. Based on the agreement reached with the management of the companies convenience sampling techniques were employed to administer the questionnaires specially designed for the study in order not to disrupt production activities. According Zikmund (2003), convenience data collection procedure ensures that a large number of respondents participate and complete questionnaires in quick and economical manner.

Validation Test of Instrument: In a bid to validate the instrument, 40 items drawn in the first version of the questionnaire were given to experts with background in management and economics for content validation (Nunnally, 1967). The experts were requested to indicate on a scale of 1 to 5, the extent to which they considered the items as valid measures of the various constructs in the study. Out of the original 40 items, 24 items with scores of 4 and above were accepted as valid.

Reliability Test of Instrument: For the testing the reliability of the study instrument, the 24 items which were outcome of the validation exercise were further subjected to item-total correlation leading to retaining 12 items based on coefficient range of 0.37-0.94 as prescribed in Rust and Golombok (1995). The reliability coefficient value obtained for the constructs include 0.87, 0.91, 0.84 and 0.81 for on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship respectively.

Method of Data Analysis: By aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22, the demographic characteristics of the respondents and research questions were presented in forms of tabulation, frequency and percentages. However, the choice of statistics for the formulated hypotheses was guided by the nature and type of the each hypothesis (Odetunde, 2011). To this end, hypotheses were tested through regression analysis. The choice of regression analysis was informed by the nature of the hypotheses formulated which dealt with test of cause and effect.

Model Specification and Justification: The statistical model specification for the regression analysis is presented below:

$$D_v = f(iv)$$

$$P = F(OJ1 + OFJ2 + Tech3 + Ment4)$$

$$P = \alpha + \beta_1(OJ1) + \beta_2(OFJ2) + \beta_3(Tech3) + \beta_4(Ment4)$$

where p = Productivity
 α = constant
 β = coefficient of x
 $OJ1$ = on-the-job training
 $OFJ2$ = off-the-job training
 $Tech3$ = Technological Knowledge Acquisition
 $Ment4$ = Organisational Mentorship

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

In carrying out the research, a total of 369 questionnaires were distributed among the employees of both Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc out of which 360 questionnaires were validly completed and returned for data analysis and interpretation. Out of these (as could be seen in table 3), 58.9% are males while 41.1% are females; this shows that both genders were represented in the study. Age of respondents in the study varied from 20 years and above with age bracket of 30-39 years being the modal age.

Respondents were asked to provide their educational background, among which 24.2% were in the National Diploma category, 23.6% identified with Higher National Diploma Certificate, 36.1% were first degree holders while 16.1% hold Master's degree. This shows that the respondents are well educated to know the relevance and implication of the study. Category of the employees varies

from junior to senior staff. In terms of representation, 58.9% of the respondents were from junior category while 41.1% were from senior staff category. Furthermore, 30.6% of the respondents were non-core employees while 69.4% were core employees.

With regard to years of experience, 29.2% of the respondents have worked with two organizations (Nigerian

Breweries and Guinness Nigeria Plc) for between 1-5 years, 20.0% for between 6-10 years, 18.9% for between 11-15 years, 17.8% for 16-20 years while 14.2% for between 21 years and above. Thus it can be inferred that majority of the respondents have been with the organizations for an upward of 10 years.

Table 3: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	212	58.9
	Female	148	41.1
	Total	360	100.0
Age at last birthday		Frequency	Percent
Valid	20-29 years	97	26.9
	30-39 years	155	43.1
	40-49 years	58	16.1
	50-59 years	50	13.9
	Total	360	100.0
Highest Educational Qualification		Frequency	Percent
Valid	ND	87	24.2
	HND	85	23.6
	Bachelors' Degree	130	36.1
	Master's Degree	58	16.1
	Total	360	100.0
Employment Type		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Non-Core Staff	110	30.6
	Core Staff	250	69.4
	Total	360	100.0
Category of Employment		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Junior Staff	212	58.9
	Senior Staff	148	41.1
	Total	360	100.0
Working Experience		Frequency	Percent
Valid	1-5 years	105	29.2
	6-10 years	72	20.0
	11-15 years	68	18.9
	16-20 years	64	17.8
	21 years and above	51	14.2
	Total	360	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2017

The Respondents' view in Relation to on-the-job training in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc

The analysis on Table 4 shows that 36.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that job rotation is carried in their organisation as means of improving employee skills and experience, 34.2% merely agreed, 4.7% were not sure, 13.0% disagreed, and 12.5% strongly disagreed. This indicates that job rotation is carried in the two organisations as means of improving employee skills and experience. In addition, 41.7% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees are given apprenticeship opportunities in their organisation, 33.1% merely agreed, 0.8% were not sure, 12.5% disagreed and 11.9% strongly disagreed. This indicates that employees are given apprenticeship opportunities in the two organisations. Furthermore, 26.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees are exposed to job instruction technology as measure of building up their expertise, 45.0% merely agreed 3.3% were not sure, 13.6% disagreed and 11.9% strongly disagreed. This indicates that employees are exposed to job instruction technology as measure of building up their expertise in the two organisations.

Table 4 - Observed Responses on on-the-job training in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	N	D	SD	TOTAL
Q7	Job rotation is carried in this organisation as means of improving employee skills and experience	128 (35.6)	123 (34.2)	17 (4.7)	47 (13.0)	45 (12.5)	360 (100)
Q8	Employees are given apprenticeship opportunities in this organisation	150 (41.7)	119 (33.1)	3 (0.8)	45 (12.5)	43 (11.9)	360 (100)
Q9	Employees are exposed to job instruction technology as measure of building up their expertise	94 (26.1)	162 (45.0)	12 (3.3)	49 (13.6)	43 (11.9)	360 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Note: The figures in bracket indicate the percentage while figures not in bracket indicate frequency

The Respondents' view in Relation to off-the-job training in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc**Table 5 - Observed Responses on off-the-job training in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc**

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	N	D	SD	TOTAL
Q10	Employees are sent on refresher courses in this organisation	128 (35.5)	123 (34.2)	17 (4.7)	47 (13.1)	45 (12.5)	360 (100)
Q11	This organisation sponsors employees on conferences to improve their capacity	150 (41.6)	119 (33.1)	3 (0.8)	45 (12.5)	43 (11.9)	360 (100)
Q12	Vestibule trainings are conducted for employees by this organisation	94 (26.1)	162 (45.0)	12 (3.3)	49 (13.6)	43 (11.9)	360 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017**Note:** The figures in bracket indicate the percentage while figures not in bracket indicate frequency

The analysis on Table 5 shows that 35.5% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees are sent on refresher courses in this organisation, 34.2% merely agreed, 4.7% were not sure, 13.1% disagreed, and 12.5% strongly disagreed. This indicates that employees are sent on refresher courses in this organisation. In addition, 41.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that their organisation sponsors employees on conferences to improve employee capacity, 33.1% merely agreed, 0.8% were not sure, 12.5% disagreed and 11.9% strongly disagreed. This indicates that their organisation sponsors employees on conferences to improve their capacity. Furthermore, 26.1% of the respondents strongly agree that vestibule training are conducted for employees by their organisation, 45.0% merely agreed 3.3% were not sure, 13.6% disagreed and 11.9% strongly disagreed. This indicates that vestibule trainings are conducted for employees by their organisation.

The Respondents' view in Relation to technological knowledge acquisition in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc**Table 6 - Observed Responses on technological knowledge acquisition in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc**

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	N	D	SD	TOTAL
Q13	Computer knowledge is a prerequisite for employment in this organisation	129 (35.8)	126 (35.0)	13 (3.6)	52 (14.4)	40 (11.1)	360 (100)
Q14	Employees in this organisation are knowledgeable about the operations of the job instruction technology	152 (42.2)	115 (31.9)	4 (1.1)	44 (12.2)	45 (12.5)	360 (100)
Q15	Employees in this organisation know how to operate the internet, intranet and other IT enablers such as the Human Resource Information System (HRIS)	94 (26.1)	162 (45.0)	12 (3.3)	49 (13.6)	43 (11.9)	360 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017**Note:** The figures in bracket indicate the percentage while figures not in bracket indicate frequency

The analysis on Table 6 shows that 35.8% of the respondents strongly agreed that computer knowledge is a prerequisite for employment in their organisation, 35.0% merely agreed, 3.6% were not sure, 14.4% disagreed, and 11.1% strongly disagreed. This indicates that computer knowledge is a prerequisite for employment in their organisation. In addition, 42.2% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees in their organisation are knowledgeable about the operations of the job instruction technology, 31.9% merely agreed, 1.1% were not sure, 12.2% disagreed and 12.5% strongly disagreed. This indicates that the employees are knowledgeable about the operations of the job instruction technology. Furthermore, 26.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees know how to operate the internet, intranet and other IT enablers such as the Human Resource Information System (HRIS), 45.0% merely agreed 3.3% were not sure, 13.6% disagreed and 11.9% strongly disagreed. This indicates that the respondents know how to operate the internet, intranet and other IT enablers such as the Human Resource Information System (HRIS).

The Respondents' View in Relation to Organisational Mentoring in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc**Table 7: Observed responses on organisational mentoring in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc**

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	N	D	SD	TOTAL
Q16	Understudy is a common feature of skill acquisition this organisation	142 (39.4)	120 (33.3)	8 (2.2)	49 (13.6)	41 (11.4)	360 (100)
Q17	In order to build capacity superiors are allowed to coach their subordinates in this organisation	146 (40.6)	123 (34.2)	4 (1.1)	44 (12.2)	43 (11.9)	360 (100)
Q18	In this organisation, employees are seconded to experienced superiors in order to acquire relevant skills and competencies	94 (26.1)	162 (45.0)	12 (3.3)	48 (13.3)	44 (12.2)	360 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017**Note:** The figures in bracket indicate the percentage while figures not in bracket indicate frequency

The analysis on Table 7 shows that 39.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that understudy is a common feature of skill acquisition their organisation, 33.3% merely agreed, 2.2% were not sure, 13.6% disagreed, and 11.4% strongly disagreed. This indicates that understudy is a common feature of skill acquisition the organisations. In addition, 40.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that in order to build capacity superiors are allowed to coach their subordinates in their organisation, 34.2% merely agreed, 1.1% were not sure, 12.2% disagreed and 11.9% strongly disagree. This indicates that in order to build capacity superiors are allowed to coach their subordinates. Furthermore, 26.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that employees are seconded to experienced superiors in order to acquire relevant skills and competencies, 45.0% merely agreed 3.3% were not

sure, 13.3% disagreed and 12.2% strongly disagreed. This indicates that employees are seconded to experienced superiors in order to acquire relevant skills and competencies.

The Respondents' View in Relation to productivity in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc

Table 8: The observed responses on productivity in Nigerian Breweries Plc and Guinness Nigeria Plc

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	N	D	SD	TOTAL
Q19	Customers are provided with quality goods and services in this company	133 (36.9)	118 (32.8)	13 (3.6)	49 (13.6)	47 (13.1)	360 (100)
Q20	There are constant ways of improving service delivery in this company	147 (40.8)	122 (33.9)	3 (0.8)	42 (11.7)	46 (12.8)	360 (100)
Q21	Our company is known for the ability to retain employees who make the difference	102 (28.3)	164 (45.6)	08 (2.2)	41 (11.4)	45 (12.5)	360 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Note: The figures in bracket indicate the percentage while figures not in bracket indicate frequency

The analysis on Table 8 shows that 36.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that customers are provided with quality goods and services in the companies, 32.8% merely agreed, 3.6% were not sure, 13.6% disagreed, and 13.1% strongly disagreed. This indicates that customers are provided with quality goods and services in the companies. In addition, 40.8% of the respondents strongly agreed that there are constant ways of improving service delivery in the companies, 33.9% merely agreed, 0.8% were not sure, 11.7% disagreed and 12.8% strongly disagree. This indicates that companies seek constant ways of improving service delivery. Furthermore, 28.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that their companies are known for the ability to retain employees who make the difference, 45.6% merely agreed 2.2% were not sure, 11.4% disagreed and 12.5% strongly disagreed. This indicates that their companies retain employees who make the difference.

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses postulated that "factors like trust, love, respect, affection, cooperation, tolerance, selflessness and understanding will not significantly contribute to marital stability among health worker." The above stated hypothesis was tested using the multiple regressions with level of significance set at 0.05. The result is presented on the table below.

Table 9: Results of Simple Regression showing the contributions of each component of capacity building on productivity in the Nigerian alcoholic beverage sector

Model	Standardized Unstandardized Coefficients				
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	Sig.
(Constant)	10.148	1.507		6.736	.000
On-the-job training	1.290	0.259	.343	4.975	.000
Off-the-job training	1.440	0.306	.159	1.908	.058
Technological knowledge acquisition	2.185	0.570	.395	3.832	.000
Organisational mentorship	1.976	0.701	.350	2.818	.005

Dependent variable: Productivity

The significant t-β values for each component as seen in table 9 indicates that each component of capacity building as operationalised exerted a measure of significant influence on

productivity. This implies that hypotheses I, II, III and IV were accepted. Thus, it could be established that there is significant effect of on-the-job-training, off-the-job-training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship on productivity. However, technological knowledge acquisition exerted the highest impact on productivity with Beta weight of 39.5%. This is closely followed by organisational mentorship (Beta weight = 35.0%), on-the-job training (Beta weight = 34.3%) and off-the-job training (Beta weight = 15.9%) with the least contribution.

Table 10: Moderated Regression Analysis showing the effect of capacity building on productivity in the Nigerian alcoholic beverage sector

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	F	R	R ²	Adj-R ²	ΔR ²
Productivity	Capacity Building	11.8 46*	.51 9*	.26 9*	.24 6	26. 9*

It could be observed from table 10 that on account of the combined influence of on-the-job-training, off-the-job-training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship, capacity building accounted for 26.9% of variations on productivity in the Nigerian alcoholic beverage sector. The predictability strength and variation among the individual components of capacity building on productivity among in the Nigerian alcoholic beverage sector was further established by the significant F-value (F= 11.846; = 0.000). This implies that hypothesis V which stated that capacity building effected significantly on productivity was confirmed.

Discussion of Findings

This segment presented responses obtained from respondents on the effect of capacity building on productivity using selected companies using Nigerian Breweries Plc Lagos and Guinness Nigeria Plc Lagos as case studies. In relation to test of hypotheses, the outcome of the Regression analyses conducted confirmed all the formulated hypotheses in the study. Specifically, the first and second of the results obtained imply that there is significant effects of on-the-job-training and off-the-job-training on productivity. This particular result is in consonance with earlier studies such as Singh and Mohanty (2012), Nda and Frad (2013), Sabir, Akhtar, Bukhari, Nasir and Ahmed (2014), Ombayo, Egezza and Shiamwama (2014), Eneh, Inyang, and Ekpe (2014), Obi-Anike and Ekwe (2014), Kim and Polyhart (2014) and Falola, Osibanjo and Ojo (2014) which linked consistent learning and upgrading of skills and competence

which come from formal and informal training opportunities to productivity in the organisation.

In testing the third hypotheses, the study also discovered that there is significant effect of technological knowledge acquisition on productivity. This result is in line with existing literature such as Dauda and Akingbade (2011), Oluwagbemi, Abah and Achimugu (2011) and Berisha-Shaqiri (2015) which reported that technological knowledge acquisition has revolutionised the conduct of businesses such that employees are productively deployed by organizations to obtain strategic advantage

In relation to the fourth hypothesis, the study found that there is significant effect of organisational mentorship on productivity. This particular result is supported by earlier studies such as Kahle-Piasecki (2011), Tewari and Sharma (2014), Mba and Godday (2015) and Tanoli (2016) which found that mentoring relationships impact on productivity by improving employee skills and competence. Finally, the study revealed through the fifth hypothesis that there is significant effect of capacity building on productivity. This particular result is in tandem with extant literature such as Igbaekemen (2014), Ojukuku and Adegbite (2014), Wanyama and Mutsotso (2010) and Yamoah and Maiyo (2014) which established that improved productivity in the organisation could be achieved by building employee capacities.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The study focused on the effect of capacity building on productivity using the two leading players in the alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Nigeria (Nigeria Breweries Plc., Lagos and Guinness Nigeria Plc) as case study. In line with extant literature capacity building which constituted the independent variable in the study was operationalised in terms of on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship as its components. Survey design, systematic and stratified sampling techniques were employed to draw a sample of three hundred and sixty (360) respondents who participated in the study. Data was collected using validated scales designed for the purpose of this study. Five (5) hypotheses were formulated and tested using simple and multiple regression analysis namely that there is no significant impacts of on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship on productivity and that there is no significant impact of capacity building on productivity. The results showed that the four dimensions of the independent variable (i.e. on-the-job training, off-the-job training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship) impacted significantly on productivity in the study population. Furthermore, the multiple regression analysis conducted confirmed these results as capacity building was also found to have effected significantly on productivity. These findings support the notion that enabling employees with the right blend of skills, knowledge, expertise and experience would be in the firm's best productive interests.

Conclusion

The first and second conclusions reached from the study are that there is significant effects of on-the-job-training and off-

the-job training on productivity. The implication of this conclusion is that it is to the (competitive) productive advantage of the organisationa when employees are afforded opportunities to acquire real time experiences in performing organisational roles such as in-role playing and job-enrichment. In the same vein, it could be conclude that formal training opportunities such as education, workshops, seminars, conferences, retreats etc. can equip employees with the necessary skills, competences and efficiency needed in the productive endeavours of the organisation (Singh & Mohanty, 2012, Nda & Frad, 2013; Sabir, Akhtar, Bukhari, Nasir & Ahmed, 2014; Ombayo, Egessa & Shiamwama, 2014; Eneh, Inyang, & Ekpe, 2014; Obi-Anike & Ekwe, 2014; Kim & Polyhart, 2014; Falola, Osibanjo & Ojo, 2014).

Thirdly from the study, it is concluded that there is significant effect of technological knowledge acquisition on productivity. The implication of this finding is that capacity building via technological knowledge is a formidable way of making the organisation competitive (Ngure & Njuri, 2013; Dauda & Akingbade, 2011, Oluwagbemi, Abah & Achimugu, 2011; Berisha-Shaqiri, 2015). Furthermore, the study showed that there is significant effect of organisational mentorship on productivity. In essence, when less experienced employees are encouraged to continuously learn from their superiors through exposure and guidance, the organisation would be better for it productively (Kahle-Piasecki, 2011; Tewari & Sharma, 2014; Mba & Godday, 2015; Tanoli, 2016). Finally from the study, it is concluded that there is significant effect of capacity building on productivity. To this end, it could be positd that if the firm adopts on-the-job-training, off-the-job-training, technological knowledge acquisition and organisational mentorship capacity as measures to build employee capacities; such developments would not only assist employees in acquiring new skills but also improving on the already acquired skills thereby leading to the overall productive benefits of the enterprise (Igbaekemen, 2014; Ojukuku & Adegbite, 2014; Wanyama & Mutsotso, 2010; Yamoah & Maiyo, 2014).

Recommendations

In view of the findings which linked capacity building with productivity in selected organizations in the Nigerian alcoholic beverage sector, the study therefore recommends as follows:

- I. Our findings showed that the both on-the-job and off-the-job trainings effect on productivity. To this end, the study recommends that cost implications notwithstanding, value-based training should be provided to build employee capacities which should be implemented by on-the-job exposure to develop employee skill, experience, mind-set and competence.
- II. In line with the third finding and for organizations to fully reap the gains of this age, of globalization, it is recommended that it is in the productive interest of organizations to technologically expose its employees to accumulate the right skills, knowledge and expertise in order to build their productive capacities.
- III. It is recommended that organisation should design mentoring arrangements whereby less experienced employees would be able to learn from their more experienced counterpart with appropriate channels opened for feedback.
- IV. Furthermore, as business competitions become increasingly knowledge based, it is recommended that

firms need to selectively acquire and nurture the best and brightest human capital available and ensure that they are retained through competitive compensation.

- V. Finally, it is recommended that organisations should elevate capacity building to the status of business strategy.

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